

Event Abstract

Nutritional Status Assessment in Autistic Children Using Somatic Measurements “A Field Study of the Zliten Autistic Children”

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The somatic measurements of human are important to the determination of the nutritional status in all stages of age, especially the development and growth of children. Therefore, the objective of the present study to identify the nutritional status of Zliten autistic children using somatic measurements. This study was conducted only on autistic children from autism schools in Zliten city. The search sample consists of (65) children aged 4 to 14 years. Their some somatic parameters had been measured such as length, weight, the circumference of the head, chest, wrist and also BMI. The results have shown that (78.46%) were males, whereas (21.54 %) were females, and also found 50 % of the children ranged in age from 8 to 11 years. Calculating the body mass index (BMI) showed that 67.93 % of children had thin BMI, whereas 24.53 % of children are normal BMI. The autism level was (46.03 %) for each level (1) and level (2). It was also found that the study search sample had (36.92%) and (33.84 %) social isolation and aggressiveness respectively. The development and growth of children during nutritional Status is an important issue and needs to be followed up by family and health-care teams.

Keywords: Nutritional Status, Somatic Measurements, Autistic Children.

Conference: 4th Libyan Conference on Medical and Pharmaceutical sciences 2020 (4th LCMPS2020) “Crossings Frontiers in The Field of Medicine and Pharmaceutical Science”, Janzur, Libya, 14 Nov, 2020.

Presentation Type: Oral Presentation

Citation: Keri Ighwela. Nutritional Status Assessment in Autistic Children Using Somatic Measurements “A Field Study of the Zliten Autistic Children”, Alq J Med App Sci. 2020;3(3):10. Conference Abstract: Fourth Libyan Conference on Medical and Pharmaceutical sciences 2020 (4th LCMPS2020) “Crossings Frontiers in The Field of Medicine and Pharmaceutical Science”.

doi: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4096703>

Received: 31 Mar 2020; **Published Online:** 1 Nov 2020.

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